

Anti-Racism–Health Policy Statistics Implications: Alignment with Health Policy and Health Services Research Initiatives

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Abstract

The creation of the American Statistical Association's Antiracism Task Force was motivated by a deep-seated concern over racial injustices that exist in our society, which spill over into our work and contributions as statisticians, data scientists, and quantitative researchers. The goal is to make the Association more just, equitable, diverse, and inclusive by identifying ways in which the Association's leadership, organizational structure, policies, practices, membership, outreach efforts, and guidance on the responsible use of statistics can advance racial justice by becoming more antiracist. Attention is given to the ASA Task Force on Anti-Racism, its health policy statistics implications, and its alignment with health policy and health services research initiatives

Key Words: ASA Task Force on Anti-Racism; health policy; equity; health disparities.

1. Introduction

The creation of the American Statistical Association's Antiracism Task Force was motivated by a deep-seated concern over racial injustices that exist in our society, which spill over into our work and contributions as statisticians, data scientists, and quantitative researchers. The goal is to make the Association more just, equitable, diverse, and inclusive by identifying ways in which the Association's leadership, organizational structure, policies, practices, membership, outreach efforts, and guidance on the responsible use of statistics can advance racial justice by becoming more antiracist. In this paper, attention is given to the ASA Task Force on Anti-Racism, its health policy statistics implications, and its alignment with health policy and health services research initiatives.

2. Background

There are visible ongoing efforts by ASA to advance equity, diversity, and inclusivity both within the organization and in statistical practice. The charge of the ASA Task Force on Anti-Racism was to help align the Association's activities to achieve its antiracism vision. The Task Force Report provides a summary of its findings and recommendations to address the challenges at hand. Consequently, there are multifold opportunities for greater alignment with health policy and health services research initiatives. These include prioritizing partnerships with organizations that demonstrate a shared value for justice, equity, diversity, and inclusion; public sector initiatives to advance health equity and address health disparities; and addressing analytical/study design and research challenges.

3. Addressing ASA Task Force Recommendations for Partnerships

Multiple organizations, institutes, and foundations are advancing efforts to promote diversity, equity, and inclusion in health services and policy research. One such organization is AcademyHealth, which is committed to promoting diversity and equity among its members and the health services research opportunity. In this vein, it created an advisory group on Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in Health Services and Policy Research (DEI) in HSR to enhance the organization's priorities and activities for meaningful change. In addition, the organization's Methods and Data Council serves to identify trends, opportunities, challenges, and needs related to existing and emerging methods used in health services research and associated with DEI initiatives.

Another organization that is advancing efforts to promote diversity, equity, and inclusion in health is the American Public Health Association (APHA). The mission of the American Public Health Association (APHA) is to improve the health of the public and achieve equity in health status. The association advocates on a range of social determinants and stressors related to structural racism and racial and ethnic discrimination as a public health crisis. Its policy statement is that Structural Racism is a Public Health Crisis. It advances studies such as the Public Health Impact of Racism, which serves to shape both opportunity and access to resources that support health; contributes to growing health disparities between and across communities. Furthermore, the organization's Committee on Health Equity charged with ensuring that APHA meets its diversity, inclusion, and social justice goals by monitoring the diversity of its Sections, Committees, Councils, and Boards. APHA also has an Applied Public Health Statistics Section that serves as a focal point that identifies issues, develops strategies, and promotes activities in the area of statistics. Several members of the ASA Health Policy Statistics Section are also members and these connections serve as a catalyst for advancing partnerships to advance diversity, equity, and inclusion in health.

The Robert Wood Johnson Foundation (RWJF) is committed to building a Culture of Health that provides everyone in America a fair and just opportunity for health and well-being. RWJF efforts in support of achieving this goal necessitate a focus on equity, diversity, and inclusion. The Foundation is working to help achieve health equity and expand opportunity to pursue the best health possible through investments in four broad areas: Health Systems; Health Communities; Healthy Children and Families; and Leadership for Better Health. In addition, its Equity and Social Justice Relationships (ESJR) strategy seeks to dismantle the impact of structural racism on health and advance a Culture of Health. It also supports Innovative Research to Advance Racial Equity through its Evidence for Action initiative.

4. Public Sector Initiatives to Advance Health Equity and Address Health Disparities

The Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) is committed to addressing inequities and advancing equity through assessing and changing policies, programs, and processes across the Department. These efforts help shift efforts and approaches to institutionalize and sustain a focus on equity over time. In particular, Health and Human Services (HHS) has developed an Equity Action Plan to help advance equity in the delivery of health and human services. Examples of specific actions by HHS to advance equity focus on the areas of civil rights and language access, acquisitions, grants, capacity building, and maternal mortality. Efforts focusing on civil rights protections will help address barriers to health care and human services faced by individuals with limited English proficiency in obtaining information, services and/or benefits. Attention to acquisitions and

grants will help facilitate increased opportunities to HHS contracting for small disadvantaged businesses and Historically Underutilized Business Zone Small Businesses, and support incorporating equity considerations into Notice of Funding Opportunities. In addition, the prioritization of action on maternal mortality action will be focused on addressing the increased pregnancy and postpartum morbidity and mortality among Black and American Indian/ Alaska Native (AI/AN) pregnant and childbearing individuals.

<https://www.hhs.gov/sites/default/files/hhs-equity-action-plan.pdf>

In addition to these Departmental efforts, specific Agencies and Institutes are engaged in aligned efforts to advance health equity and address health disparities. The National Institutes of Health (NIH) supports programs to improve the diversity of the scientific workforce with the goal of harnessing the complete intellectual capital of the nation. NIH also recently launched the [UNITE Initiative](#) in February 2021 to address structural racism in biomedical research. This initiative includes increasing investments over the next 10 years to address structural racism; increasing transparency of NIH race and ethnicity data of NIH grant recipients; expanding grant programs and funding to enhance faculty and student diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility at higher education institutions; and requiring the development of plans to enhance equity at all NIH Institutes and Centers.

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) also plays a critical role in addressing racism and the resulting health inequities. These initiatives to address health inequities rooted in racism includes a focus on scientific research, community programs, policy efforts, and workforce development. This includes acquiring a better understanding of the social determinants of health and addressing the racial and ethnic health inequities illuminated throughout the COVID-19 pandemic.

<https://www.cdc.gov/minorityhealth/racism-disparities/cdc-efforts.html>

The mission of the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality's (AHRQ) is to produce evidence to make health care safer, higher quality, more accessible, equitable, and affordable. In this regard, the Agency has released a Special Emphasis Notice to receive health services research grant applications that propose innovative and evidence-based interventions that advance the nation's goal of achieving equity in the delivery of healthcare services. For over two decades, AHRQ and HHS have reported on national healthcare quality and disparities through the *National Healthcare Quality and Disparities Report*. The report presents trends for measures related to access to care, affordable care, care coordination, effective treatment, healthy living, patient safety, and person-centered care.

5. Health Disparities' Impact on Cancer Patients

Improving health outcomes in cancer patients is challenged by health disparities that impact specific populations such as racial minorities and economically disadvantaged population subgroups. Clinical trials are often conducted among younger, healthier, and less racially diverse patients than the population at large. Health disparities for individuals with cancer are most apparent when there are notable differences in the occurrence, frequency, burden of cancer, and mortality rates among specific population groups. The ASA Task Force on Anti-Racism Report includes discussion of how clinicians and healthcare could better incorporate recruitment of underrepresented groups into clinical trials and makes note of the limited resources to help increase the enrollment of vulnerable and underrepresented populations in clinical trials.

Finding O1: Many organizations have statistics and data science as a major component of their work which implies that they have a responsibility to think about the ethical use of statistics, including the use of statistics and data science in an antiracist manner (subcommittee discussed how clinicians and healthcare could better incorporate recruitment of underrepresented groups into clinical trials, DEI in Clinical Research...)

Finding T6: There are limited resources to help increase the enrollment of vulnerable and underrepresented populations in clinical trials (NIH Women and Minorities, FDA Minority Health Equity Resources).

Health disparities for individuals with cancer are most apparent when there are notable differences in the occurrence, frequency, death, and burden of cancer among specific population groups, which often are manifest when comparing the experiences of distinct racial and ethnic minority groups. Poverty, lack of access to prevention/detection services, and the unavailability of high-quality treatment are factors that influence such differentials in patient outcomes. Consequently, research efforts that focus on the determinants of health disparities depend on the availability of information that distinguish cancer patients by demographic and socioeconomic factors, their access to health care services and treatments, and their health behaviors.

Project Data Sphere, LLC (PDS) was formed in 2012 to catalyze cancer research by bringing together diverse minds and technologies to help unleash the full potential of existing clinical trial data. PDS, an independent initiative of the CEO Roundtable on Cancer's (CEORT's) Life Sciences Consortium, operates a first-of-its-kind research platform. PDS provides the research community with broad access to both de-identified patient-level data from oncology clinical trials and freely available analytic tools to assist them in analyzing those data.

A primary goal of PDS is to advance new research efforts that will improve the lives of cancer patients and their families around the world (1, 2). These data are rich in measures that characterize the clinical trials under study, treatment protocols, and patient outcomes. However, to address the confidentiality provisions inherent to the trials, data providers are required to de-identify patient-level data prior to uploading datasets to ProjectDataSphere.org by masking or removing certain demographic data. Consequently, the influence of health-related and socioeconomic factors, access to and use of health care services, and predisposition of health behaviors on treatment effects and patient outcomes cannot currently be assessed. The inclusion of these measures would significantly enhance the analytic capacity and utility of the PDS data, further stimulating hypothesis generation and the initiation of new studies that explore these relationships.

To address these analytic constraints, the data profiles in selected PDS patient-level cancer phase III clinical datasets have been augmented by linking the social, economic, and health-related characteristics of like cancer survivors from nationally representative health and health care-related survey data from the national Medical Expenditure Panel Survey (MEPS) sponsored by the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality. MEPS was designed to provide national population-based health care use, expenditure, and source of payment estimates in addition to measures of health status, demographic characteristics, employment, health insurance coverage, and access to health care. Using statistical linkage and model-based techniques, patient-level records in selected PDS datasets have been linked to those of comparable cancer survivors, and are thereby augmented with survey

content on social, economic, and health-related characteristics. The PDS-MEPS data integration permits studies that examine:

Whether the demographic characteristics of those cancer patients enrolled in specific phase III clinical trials comparable to cancer patients with the same disease in the general population?

How are variations in cancer patients' access to health care and income impacting patient outcomes in specific phase III clinical trials?

What variations in patient outcomes are associated with specific demographic, socioeconomic, and health-related factors, including health preferences?

6. Implementation opportunities in health policy statistics

The American Statistical Association's Antiracism Task Force Report indicates there are limited available research related to specific topics of interest including racial-ethnic bias in problem framing and in samples (Finding T5). Future opportunities and initiatives to address these challenges include the following:

- Attention to oversampling strategies in national surveys and research studies to yield sufficient statistical power necessary to conduct studies of health disparities.
- Consideration of “hybrid” sample designs that benefit by data integration innovations to address representational limitations.
- The pooling of relevant data over time incorporating model-based adjustments that incorporate impact of secular trends.
- Ensuring the adequate representation of individuals with multiple chronic conditions to inform assessments of health disparities.
- Facilitating reductions in racial bias in AI by employing diverse teams in the development of AI models and requiring the use of large, diverse training sets.
- Improvements to the measurement of structural racism.
- Improvements in the deciphering the distinct and interacting components of the Social Determinants of Health (SDOH): economic stability; environment; education; health care access and quality; community and the impacts of racism, discrimination, and violence.
- Conduct of intersectional studies that assess the impacts of racism in tandem with other obstacles to advance our knowledge of health disparities.
- Improved predictive modeling techniques to better inform the short- and long-term impacts of potentially corrective interventions.

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